

A new species of *Anatoma* (Vetigastropoda: Anatomidae) from the Strait of Gibraltar

Una nueva especie de Anatoma (Vetigastropoda: Anatomidae) del estrecho de Gibraltar

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859, collected by the BALGIM expedition (1984) from the Atlantic entrance of the Strait of Gibraltar is described and figured. The new species is compared with other *Anatoma* species reported in this and other areas, from which it is distinguished by the axial sculpture of the shell with unusually numerous ribs. The large number of species of this genus found in the studied area highlights the importance of deep-sea research, revealing unexpected biodiversity and suggesting further exploration opportunities.

RESUMEN

Se describe e ilustra una nueva especie del género *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859, recolectada por la expedición BALGIM (1984) en la entrada atlántica del estrecho de Gibraltar. Se compara la nueva especie con otras especies de *Anatoma* citadas en esta y otras zonas, de las que se diferencia por la escultura de la concha compuesta por costillas axiales en número mucho mayor de lo habitual. El elevado número de especies de este género encontradas en el área estudiada resalta la importancia de la investigación en aguas profundas, revela una inesperada biodiversidad y sugiere nuevas oportunidades de exploración.

KEY WORDS: Vetigastropoda, Anatomidae, taxonomy, Strait of Gibraltar, endemism.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Vetigastropoda, Anatomidae, taxonomía, estrecho de Gibraltar, endemismo.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Anatoma* comprises small vetigastropods formerly placed in the family Scissurellidae, until GEIGER & JANSEN (2004) raised the subfamily Anatominae McLean, 1989 to family level, arguing that Scissurellinae is the sister

group to Lepetodrilidae plus Clypeosectidae in a crown clade with Haliotidae, whereas Anatominae is amongst the most basal Vetigastropoda together with Pleurotomariidae. A closer attention and the support of imaging techniques using

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Figure 1. Map of the Ibero-Moroccan area showing the position of the collecting stations studied herein (coloured symbols). AAIW: Antarctic Intermediate Water (flowing northwards along the Moroccan margin); MOW: Mediterranean Outflow Water.

Figura 1. Mapa del área ibero-marroquí que muestra la posición de las estaciones de muestreo estudiadas aquí (símbolos con color). AAIW: Agua Antártica Intermedia (que fluye hacia el norte a lo largo del margen marroquí); MOW: Agua Mediterránea saliente.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) has shown this genus to be diverse, with 90 recent species worldwide (WoRMS, 2024), of which 54 have been described in this century and only 13 were already known in the XIXth century. GEIGER (2012) provided the first global revision of “little slit shells” in which he described and imaged all hitherto known species. In European seas, *Anatoma crispata* (Fleming, 1828), the type species of the genus, was for a long time considered to be the only representative of the genus, whereas 17 species are now recognized.

The Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and the Alboran Sea are areas of extraordinary hydrological complexity, united by the narrow Strait of Gibraltar (Fig. 1) and a concomitantly diverse fauna. Within the Alboran Sea, incoming Atlantic Water occupies the superficial levels down to a maximum depth of ca. 150-200 m in the northern part and constitutes two anticyclonic gyres. The deeper part of the Alboran Sea is occupied by west-

ward moving Mediterranean Deep Waters, which merge into a single plume to feed the outgoing Mediterranean Outflow Water (MOW) (GASCARD & RICHEY, 1985; NARANJO *ET AL.*, 2015: 46). The highly saline MOW flows over the seafloor towards the Atlantic Ocean, crossing the Camarinal Sill at 284 m on the western side of the Strait, then extending westwards and northwards along the Iberian margin but not affecting at all the Moroccan slope. Along the NW African margin, there is instead a northwards flow of modified Antarctic Intermediate Water (AAIW) which abuts against the MOW in the same depth interval (VOELKER *ET AL.*, 2015).

Here we describe a distinctive additional species of *Anatoma* collected at the Atlantic entrance of the Strait of Gibraltar by the BALGIM expedition. We compare the new species to other previously known from the Atlantic (GEIGER, 2012; PIMENTA & GEIGER, 2015; HOFFMAN, GOFAS & FREIWALD, 2021; HOFFMAN & FREIWALD, 2022) and

provide illustrations and notes on five species previously reported in the area: *Anatoma aspera* (Philippi, 1844), *A. eximia* (G. Seguenza, 1880), *A. micalii* Geiger, 2012, *A. tenuisculpta* (G. Seguenza, 1880), *A. umbilicata* (Jeffreys, 1883).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

BALGIM was a French oceanographic expedition set up in 1984 by the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN) of Paris (chief scientist: Philippe Bouchet), targeted to study the relationship between water masses and benthic fauna composition between the Atlantic and Mediterranean through the Strait of Gibraltar. Of a total of 125 benthic hauls, 115 (41 using the beam

trawl (CP), 74 using dredges (DR or DW)) collected molluscan specimens in a wide depth range from 115 to 2110 m depth. The coarse fractions were mostly sorted on board, whereas the finer fractions were preserved on board, sieved on 5, 2, 1, and 0.5 mm sieves, and later sorted under a stereomicroscope.

Additional comparative material was obtained from other sources. One sample (BV35, 36.003°N, -2.8325°W, 149-176 m) was collected during the LIFE+ INDEMARES Alborán project (2011-2013), aimed at documenting habitats in the proposed offshore Site of Community Importance. Another sample was collected by H. Zibrowius on July 27, 1978, in sediment of a submarine cave under Isla de Tarifa (36.000°N, -5.606°W, -18 m) in the strait of Gibraltar.

SYSTEMATIC DESCRIPTION

Genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859

Type species: *Scissurella crispata* Fleming, 1828), by monotypy.

Anatoma balgimae n. sp. (Fig. 2)

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Type material – MOROCCO • 2 specimens (syntype 1, 1.59 mm diameter; syntype 2, 1.76 mm diameter); 35.9333°N, -5.58333°W; 580 m; 17 Jun. 1984; R/V “Cryos” BALGIM DR153; MNHN-IM-2000-36202. We designate syntypes rather than a holotype and a paratype, because both specimens are in good condition, are deemed conspecific, so that we are reluctant to delete one of them as name-bearing type.

Other material examined: MOROCCO • 1 shell (1.50 mm diameter); 35.7°N, -6.5833°W; 548 m; 03 Jun. 1984; R/V “Cryos” BALGIM DW57; MNHN-IM-2000-36203.

Etymology: The name honours the expedition where the specimens were collected.

Description: Shell up to 1.76 mm in diameter, with a stepped spire and flat apex, with strongly protruding margin of selenizone; sculpture of very crowded axial cordlets and indistinct spiral threads; aperture rounded, tapering toward anal slit; suture deep; colour opaque white.

Protoconch (Fig. 2H, I) of less than one whorl, with a rough surface (“floculent sculpture” of GEIGER, 2012), transition to teleoconch clear by change of sculpture but not delimited by a rim.

Width of exposed part of protoconch 0.23 mm.

Teleoconch of 2 ¼ whorls, with slightly convex shoulder area and rounded base, selenizone distinctly above periphery and very prominent (Fig. 2A, E). Teleoconch I (from end of protoconch to start of selenizone) of ½ convex whorl, flush with protoconch; about 26 fine axial curved riblets, with an indistinct series of aligned nodes giving the hint of a spiral line abutting on the start of selenizone. Teleoconch II

(after the start of selenizone) with about 250 appressed axial riblets on the both adapical and abapical parts of the last whorl (Fig. 2A, C-E). Spiral sculpture consisting of indistinct, widely separated spiral threads, thinner than the axial riblets and not overriding them, in the middle of the adapical part and on the entire abapical part, more conspicuous towards the umbilicus (Fig. 2B, F); about 5 spiral threads adapically and 20 abapically. Selenizone with margins forming a sharply protruding ridge, smooth externally with the axial riblets fading out where abutting on the base of the ridge; strong symmetrical curved ribs within, widely separated, about half as numerous as axial ribs (Fig. 2G).

Aperture with a sharp lip, smooth inside, tapering on its outer side toward the slit which is narrow and about $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl deep. Columellar lip sharp, protruding, rounded at base, markedly narrowing where meeting parietal area. Umbilicus moderately wide, deep, with a funiculus which is distinct (Fig. 2B) but situated far inside and hardly visible in apertural view.

Remarks: This species is thoroughly different from any other previously reported in European seas, mostly by its axial sculpture of so densely set riblets that the aspect under the optical stereomicroscope (and even under SEM at low magnification: see Fig. 1C) is silky rather than sculptured. The Australian *Anatoma aupouria* (Powell, 1937) is superficially similar in size and profile (see GEIGER & JANSEN, 2004), with a similarly stepped spire, a strongly raised selenizone and broad last whorl. However, there are clearcut differences: the teleoconch I is a very short $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl with only 7 riblets, the axial sculpture extends over the raised sides of the selenizone, and the umbilical funiculus is conspicuous, among other details. The Brazilian *Anatoma campense* Pimenta & Geiger, 2015 is also similar in outline but has much fewer (ca. 80 vs. 250) axial riblets per whorl and is reported to lack a funiculus (PIMENTA & GEIGER, 2015).

All other species known in the area considered are so different that compari-

sons may be deemed superfluous. The most common of them is *Anatoma aspera* (Philippi, 1844), which has an elevated spire, a sculpture of 50-60 axial riblets much narrower than their interspaces, distinct spiral threads, and a very moderately salient selenizone (Fig. 3A-D). A single shell of *Anatoma eximia* (G. Seguenza, 1880) was found in 466 m in the northern part of Gulf of Cádiz; that species resembles *A. aspera* in having an elevated spire but is unambiguously distinguished by the elevated position of the selenizone (about mid-whorl in *A. aspera*) and by the narrow umbilicus lacking a funiculus inside (Fig. 3I, J).

Anatoma micalii Geiger, 2012 was reported from the Moroccan part of the Strait of Gibraltar (GEIGER, 2012), the Alboran Sea on Chella Bank (CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023), the Gulf of Cadiz (UTRILLA ET AL., 2020) and in a submarine cave next to Tarifa Island, Strait of Gibraltar (this study, Fig. 3 E-H). This small species also has a low, stepped profile of the spire and the raised selenizone, but the sculpture is radically different from that of *A. balgimae* n. sp. with its last whorl having only 60-100 axial riblets abapically, and only ca. 30 strong ribs on the adapical part. The Azorean shallow-water species *Anatoma janusa* Geiger, 2012 resembles *A. micalii* in many respects and therefore differs in the same way from *A. balgimae* n. sp.

A relatively large species tentatively identified as *Anatoma tenuisculpta* (following GEIGER, 2012: fig. 916C; misidentified as *Anatoma crispata* in GOFAS, MORENO & SALAS, 2011) was found on the Djibouti Banks (shells only; GOFAS ET AL., 2014) and around Alboran Island (live specimens and shells, Fig. 4A-E). It is twice as large as *A. balgimae* n. sp., has a narrow, hardly raised selenizone and the spire is low conical, with the last whorl attached to the previous one only a short distance from the suture.

The deep-water species *Anatoma umbilicata* (Jeffreys, 1884) was found represented by two shells (Fig. 4F, G) in 1182 m off Rabat, Morocco, in an area which is not influenced by the Mediterranean Outflow Water. This and the

Figure 2. *Anatoma balgimae* n. sp. Syntypes, BALGIM DR153, Strait of Gibraltar, 35.9333°N, -5.58333°W; 580 m. A: syntype 1 (diameter 1.59 mm); B: oblique view of the umbilicus of syntype 1, showing funiculus (arrow); C: syntype 1, apical view; D: syntype 2, umbilical view (diameter 1.76 mm); E: syntype 2; F: detail of framed area in D; G: detail of selenizone, framed area in E; H: apical area including teleoconch I of syntype 2; I: protoconch.

Figura 2. *Anatoma balgimae* n. sp. Sintipos, BALGIM DR153, estrecho de Gibraltar, 35,9333°N, -5,58333°W; 580 m. A: sintipo 1 (diámetro 1,59 mm); B: vista oblicua del ombligo del sintipo 1, mostrando el funículo (flecha); C: sintipo 1, vista apical; D: sintipo 2, vista umbilical (diámetro 1,76 mm); E: sintipo 2; F: detalle del área enmarcada en D; G: detalle de la selenizona, área enmarcada en E; H: área apical que incluye la teleoconcha I del sintipo 2; I: protoconcha.

similar *Anatoma pagoda* Hoffman, Gofas & Freiwald, 2021 differ from *A. balgimae* n. sp. in having a flatter profile on the adapical part of the whorls, a deep, much broader umbilicus and an attenuated axial sculpture with only ca. 90 riblets on the last whorl.

The enigmatic *Anatoma orbiculata* Geiger, 2012 (not illustrated; see GEIGER, 2012: 996-999) differs thoroughly in having a biconvex profile, and few strong, widely separated axial ribs. It was described from beach drift collected

by the second author in 1971, at the mouth of Oued el Helou just north of Asilah (Morocco; misspelled Qued el Helou, Asilha in GEIGER, 2012), and is known only from one further occurrence is southern Angola (GEIGER, 2012). This occurrence is discrepant with the usual occurrence of *Anatoma* species in circalittoral and bathyal environments. One possible explanation is that the shell could come from the cleaning of fishing gears operating down to the *Dendrophyllia* zone (ca. 180 m) off Asilah at that

Figure 3. Other *Anatoma* species reported from the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and the Alboran Sea. A-D. *Anatoma aspera* (Philippi, 1844) from INDEMARES Alboran BV35, 36.003°N, -2.8325°W, 149-176 m. A: shell (diameter 2.36 mm); B: shell (diameter 2.52 mm); C, D: details of apical part with teleoconch I and protoconch, same specimen as B. E-H. *Anatoma micalii* Geiger, 2012 from a submarine cave next to Isla de Tarifa, 36.000°N, -5.606°W, -18 m, leg. H. Zibrowius 27 Jul. 1978. E: shell (diameter 1.26 mm); F: shell (diameter 1.33 mm); G, H: details of apical part with teleoconch I and protoconch, same as F. I, J. *Anatoma eximia* (G. Seguenza, 1880) from BALGIM DR22, 36.5833°N, -7.4000°W, 466 m (height 2.92 mm).

Figura 3. Otras especies de *Anatoma* citadas para el golfo Ibero-marroquí y el mar de Alborán. A-D. *Anatoma aspera* (Philippi, 1844) de INDEMARES Alborán BV35, 36,003°N, -2,8325°W, 149-176 m. A: concha (diámetro 2,36 mm); B: concha (diámetro 2,52 mm); C, D: detalle de la parte apical con teleoconcha I y protoconcha, mismo ejemplar que B. E-H. *Anatoma micalii* Geiger, 2012 de una cueva submarina junto a la isla de Tarifa, 36,000°N, -5,606°W, -18 m, leg. H. Zibrowius 27 Jul. 1978. E: concha (diámetro 1,26 mm); F: concha (diámetro 1,33 mm); G, H: detalle de la parte apical con teleoconcha I y protoconcha, mismo que F. I, J. *Anatoma eximia* (G. Seguenza, 1880) de BALGIM DR22, 36,5833°N, -7,4000°W, 466 m (altura, 2,92 mm).

time. Another recently described species, *A. symmetrica* Hoffman, Gofas & Freiwald, 2021 from seamounts south of the Azores resembles *A. orbiculata* in having

a similar number of ribs above and below suture, but differs still more drastically from *A. balgimae* n. sp. in having less than 50 ribs in the last whorl.

Figure 4. Other *Anatoma* species reported from the Ibero-Moroccan Gulf and the Alboran Sea. A-E. *Anatoma tenuisculpta* (G. Seguenza, 1880) from INDEMARES Alboran BV35, 36.003°N, -2.8325°W, 149-176 m. A: shell (diameter 3.30 mm); B: shell (diameter 2.64 mm); C, D: details of apical part with teleoconch I and protoconch, same specimen as B; E: oblique view of the umbilicus with no funiculum, same as A. F-I. *Anatoma umbilicata* (Jeffreys, 1883) from BALGIM CP92, 34.400°N, -7.500°W, 1182 m. F: shell (diameter 2.19 mm); G: shell (diameter 2.40 mm); H, I: details of apical part with teleoconch I and protoconch, same specimen as F.

Figura 4. Otras especies de *Anatoma* citadas para el golfo Ibero-marroquí y el mar de Alborán. A-E. *Anatoma tenuisculpta* (G. Seguenza, 1880) de INDEMARES Alborán BV35, 36,003°N, -2,8325°W, 149-176 m. A: concha (diámetro 3,30 mm); B: concha (diámetro 2,64 mm); C, D: detalles de la parte apical con la teleoconcha I y de la protoconcha; E: vista oblicua del ombligo sin funículo, mismo que A. F-I. *Anatoma umbilicata* (Jeffreys, 1883), de BALGIM CP92, 34,400°N, -7,500°W, 1182 m. F: concha (diámetro 2,19; G: shell (diameter 2,40 mm); H, I: detalles de la parte apical con la teleoconcha I y la protoconcha, mismo ejemplar que en F.

DISCUSSION

The deeper part of the Strait of Gibraltar is one of the most inaccessible deep sea areas, where sampling is hindered by heavy maritime traffic and chaotic hard

bottoms with the risk of being entangled by submarine cables and other obstacles. BALGIM had two successful operations (DW152 and DW153) in the core of the

Strait, which also yielded live specimens of the recently described *Mitrella templadoi* Gofas, Luque & Urra, 2019 and of the rare epifaunal bivalve *Limopsis angusta* Jeffreys, 1879 (SALAS, 1996). There were also operations at the western entrance of the Strait, among which DW57 yielded very few specimens, but those included the rare *Manzonina alexandrei* Gofas, 2010 and one of the *Anatoma balgimae* n. sp. samples.

The type locality of *Anatoma balgimae* and *Mitrella templadoi* is situated in the core pathway of the Mediterranean Outflow Water, and this demonstrates that locations situated within this highly saline (>38 psu) water do not harbour only environmentally tolerant, widespread species. The habitat with outcrops of mud-free rock located in the aphotic zone is nevertheless quite exceptional and can only occur where the topography of the bottom is steep and currents sufficient to eliminate the fine-grained hemipelagic sediment which otherwise covers most of the bathyal sea floor. Such conditions are also met with on seamounts and other submarine elevations such as Chella Bank in the

Alboran Sea, where *Mitrella templadoi* occurs in 250-320 m on a rocky bottom (CABALLERO-HERRERA ET AL., 2023), regardless of the water mass involved. Conversely, other species such as *Anatoma umbilicata* were so far found only in cool or cold deep water such as the AAIW flowing along the Moroccan margin or NADW flowing below the Mediterranean outflow (type locality off Portugal in 1100-1800 m).

These glimpses into the deep Strait suggest that more surprises are to be expected, would the technical difficulties be overcome. Especially promising and poorly known are the deep areas surrounding the Camarinal sill and Spartel Bank at the western entrance.

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BIBLIOGRAPHY

- CABALLERO-HERRERA J.A., URRÁ J., GOFAS S., SALAS C., BÁRCENAS P., GALLARDO-NÚÑEZ M., MOYA-URBANO E., OLIVERO J. & RUEDA J.L. 2023. The molluscan fauna of Chella Bank and surroundings (Western Mediterranean Sea). *Scientia Marina*, 87 (2): e067 (27 pp.). <<https://doi.org/10.3989/scimar.05342.067>>
- GASCARD J.C. & RICHEZ C. 1985. Water masses and circulation in the western Alboran Sea and in the Straits of Gibraltar. *Progress in Oceanography*, 15 (3): 157-216.
- GEIGER D.L. 2012. Monograph of the little slit shells. Volume 1. Introduction, Scissurellidae, pp. 1-728. Volume 2. Anatomidae, Larocheidae, Depressizonidae, Sutilizonidae, Temnocinclidae. pp. 729-1291. *Santa Barbara Museum of Natural History Monographs*, 7.
- GEIGER D.L. & JANSEN P. 2004. Revision of the Australian species of Anatomidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda). *Zootaxa*, 415: 1-35.
- GOFAS S. 2010. A new *Manzonina* (Gastropoda: Rissoidae) from northwestern Morocco. *Iberus*, 28 (1): 91-96.
- GOFAS S., MORENO D. & SALAS C. 2011. *Moluscos marinos de Andalucía: I. Introducción general, clase Solenogastres, clase Caudofoveata, clase Polyplacophora y clase Gastropoda (Prosobranchia)*. Servicio de Publicaciones e Intercambio Científico, Universidad de Málaga: Málaga. ISBN 978-84-9747-381-1. pp. i,xvi, 1-342.
- GOFAS S., LUQUE Á. A. & URRÁ J. 2019. Planktotrophic Columbellidae (Gastropoda) in the northeast Atlantic and the Mediterranean Sea, with description of a new species in the genus *Mitrella*. *Bulletin of Marine Science*, 96 (1): 145-168.
- GOFAS S., SALAS C., RUEDA J.L., CANOURA J., FARIAS C. & GIL J. 2014. Mollusca from a species-rich deep-water *Leptometra* community in the Alboran Sea. *Scientia Marina*, 78 (4): 537-553.
- HOFFMAN L. & FREIWALD A. 2022. *Anatoma occidentalis* n. sp. (Vetigastropoda, Anatomidae) from upper bathyal coral habitats off western Africa. *Iberus*, 40 (2): 355-362.

- HOFFMAN L., GOFAS S. & FREIWALD A. 2021. The genus *Anatoma* Woodward, 1859 (Gastropoda, Anatomidae) from Azorean seamounts. *Iberus*, 39 (2): 139-152.
- NARANJO C., SAMMARTINO S., GARCÍA-LAFUENTE J., BELLANCO M.J. & TAUPIER-LETAGE I. 2015. Mediterranean waters along and across the Strait of Gibraltar, characterization and zonal modification. *Deep Sea Research Part I: Oceanographic Research Papers*, 105: 41-52.
- PIMENTA A.D. & GEIGER D.L. 2015. Taxonomic revision of the Anatomidae (Mollusca: Gastropoda: Vetigastropoda) from Brazil, with description of four new species. *Malacologia*, 59 (1): 135-175.
- SALAS C. 1996. Marine Bivalves from off the Southern Iberian Peninsula collected by the Balgim and Fauna 1 expeditions. *Haliothis*, 25: 33-100.
- UTRILLA O., GOFAS S., URRÁ J., MARINA P., MATEO-RAMÍREZ A., LÓPEZ-GONZÁLEZ N., GONZÁLEZ-GARCÍA E., SALAS C. & RUEDA J.L. 2020. Molluscs from benthic habitats of Gazul mud volcano (Gulf of Cádiz). *Scientia Marina*, 84 (3): 273-295.
- VOELKER A.H.L., COLMAN A., OLACK G., WANIEK J.J. & HODELL D. 2015. Oxygen and hydrogen isotope signatures of Northeast Atlantic water masses. *Deep Sea Research II: Topical Studies in Oceanography*, 116: 89e106 (18 pp.). <<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dsr2.2014.11.006>>
- WORMS EDITORIAL BOARD 2024. *World Register of Marine Species*. Accessed 2024-04-22. Available at <<http://www.marinespecies.org>>